

Polymerization of acrylamide in the layered space of montmorillonite

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Polymerization of acrylamide by Ce^{IV}-EDTA redox couple has been studied by loading Ce^{IV} ions in the interlayer space of montmorillonite. Linear termination by Ce^{IV} ions is controlled resulting in the considerable enhancement of chain growth. Kinetics of the polymerization reaction have been investigated and mechanism of the reaction is discussed.

Recently, we have demonstrated a novel technique by which chain growth is enhanced by trapping the metal oxidants in the interlayer space of montmorillonite¹. While the oxidation ability of the metal and its efficiency in activating redox polymerization of acrylamide molecules remain almost unaltered in the montmorillonite layered space, linear termination of growing polymer chain is sufficiently suppressed. This is possible because polar organic activator (thiourea) as well as the monomer could intercalate between the layer of the mineral, where the metal oxidants are present. In the previous publication, we confined our attention to the Fe^{III}-thiourea redox system and attempted to identify the pathways through which the mineral microenvironment modified the mechanism and kinetics of polymerization reaction^{1,2}. In the present paper we extend the scope of the technique and examined the effect of mineral microenvironment on Ce^{IV}-EDTA initiated aqueous acrylamide polymerization with a view to generalize the method for enhancing chain growth.

Results and Discussion

Ce^{IV}-EDTA pair is an effective initiator for the aqueous polymerization. The polymers formed by the system should carry EDTA moiety at the terminal. Recently EDTA terminated polyacrylamide was obtained by using EDTA-Ce^{IV} redox initiator in aqueous acrylamide polymerization³. The consumption rate of Ce^{IV} exhibits a first order dependence on the ceric ion concentration and follow the relation,

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k_d K[\text{EDTA}][\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/(1 + K[\text{EDTA}])$$

The complex formation constant (K) and disproportionation constant (k_d) of Ce^{IV}-EDTA chelated complex were found to be 1.07×10^4 and 3.77×10^3 , respectively³.

The rate dependence of polymerization on monomer and EDTA concentrations both follow second order kinetics in the run of monomer concentration at 0.2 mol dm⁻³. The complex constants K and k_d significantly varied with the kind of reducing agents used. The reducing agent

even influenced the behaviour of polymerization at the later stages. Further, comparatively low molecular weight polymers were formed because the polymerization reaction involves fast termination of polymer radicals by Ce^{IV} ions. Present investigation, however, shows that the polymerization mechanism is affected to a great extent if the reaction occurs in the interlayer space of the mineral. Both EDTA and acrylamide molecules intercalate into the layered space of montmorillonite where Ce^{IV} ions react with EDTA to form the initiating primary radicals. Upto 95% of polymers were formed at 50° in the presence of 1.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of Ce^{IV} ions ([EDTA] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³ and [AM] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³). The initial rate of reaction varied from 2.08×10^{-5} to 2.2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹ depending on various reaction parameters (viz. temperature, concentration of reactants etc., Table 1). The most striking feature is that while the number average molecular weight \bar{M}_n is ranged between 9.7×10^4 to 3.1×10^5 in the case of solution polymerization, montmorillonite mediated polymerization yields polymers having M_v as high as 3.9×10^5 to 2.9×10^6 . Although \bar{M}_v is always greater than \bar{M}_n , their wide difference, as observed, is intriguing. Table 1 presents the data pertaining to the initial rates (R_p), polymer yield (X_L), intrinsic viscosity (η) and molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of the polymer formed as functions of the concentrations of Ce^{IV}, EDTA, AM, pH and temperature. Molecular weight of the polymer, initial rate as well as the polymer yield, all increased with monomer concentration. Also, higher the concentration of EDTA higher is the rate of polymerization and yield but lower is the molecular weights of the polymer. On the other hand, the effect of Ce^{IV} ion concentration on R_p is remarkably different from that reported in a previous study on homogeneous polymerization by Ce^{IV}-EDTA pair. The latter showed a steady decrease in R_p with increasing Ce^{IV} concentration while the present study shows a reverse trend (Table 1). This indicates that the linear termination by Ce^{IV} ions is not important in the polymerization mechanism of the present system.

Table 1. Initial rates of polymerization, polymer yield, intrinsic viscosity and the molecular weight of Ce^{IV}-EDTA initiated polymerization on montmorillonite surface

[Ce ^{IV}] ^a 10 ³ M	MO ^b %	EDTA 10 ³ M	AM M	pH	Temp. °C	R _p ^c × 10 ⁵	X ₁ ^d %	η ml g ⁻¹	M _v × 10 ⁻⁵					
1.5	0.5	2.5	0.40	2.01	70	22.2	85	315	10.9					
					60	10.2	75	270	8.9					
					50	4.5	44	430	16.5					
					45	2.0	40	500	20.2					
1.5	0.5	2.5	0.36 0.50 0.60	2.01	50	3.0 7.9 8.9	16 40 50	145 620 650	3.9 26.9 28.7					
					1.5	0.5	5.0 7.5 10.0	0.4	2.01	50	7.0 9.7 10.6	86 89 95	300 210 240	10.2 6.4 7.6
										12.5 ^e 15.0 ^f 18.8 ^e 22.5 ^f	0.5	2.5	0.4	2.01

^aMoles of interlayer Ce^{IV} in 1000 ml of reaction mixture. ^bConcentration of montmorillonite. ^cInitial rate. ^dYield after 4.5 h. ^eMoles of interlayer Ce^{IV} in 1000 ml of montmorillonite gel.

The effect of temperature on the polymerization rate of acrylamide was investigated over the temperature range 45–70° (Table 1). The higher the temperature faster is the polymerization rate and higher is the polymer yield. On the other hand, higher the temperature lower is the molecular weight of the polyacrylamide formed. The temperature dependence of the polymerization rate followed the Arrhenius relations (Fig. 1). The overall activation energy estimated from the slope of the plot was 19.3 kcal mol⁻¹, which is close to that reported for the usual redox polymerization systems⁴.

Fig. 1. The Arrhenius plot obtained for the run of [AM] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³, [EDTA] = 0.0025 mol dm⁻³, [Ce^{IV}] = 0.0015 mol dm⁻³ and [MO] = 0.5%.

Kinetics and mechanism : The linear logarithm plot of R_p vs monomer concentration with a slope of approximately unity, indicates that the initial rate is approximately first order with respect to the monomer concentration. The significant departure of monomer exponent from 2.0 (in solution phase reaction) to 1.0 in the present solid phase reaction demands that the polymerization mechanism be reconsidered for the present condition. To examine the dependence of the rate of reaction on Ce^{IV} ion concentrations, the

initial rate of polymerization is plotted vs Ce^{IV} concentration. The concentration of Ce^{IV} in the montmorillonite gel phase was varied by adding calculated quantities of HM in the reaction mixture. (Water content of montmorillonite sample was measured to determine the gel volume of montmorillonite and found to be 10 ml g⁻¹)⁵. The slope of such logarithm plot has been estimated as 0.64 (proposed mechanism, however, predicts an exponent of 0.50, the error in the experimental data may be introduced from the inherent coarseness in following kinetics of a heterogeneous system). The slope of the linear plot of $5 + \log R_p$ vs $3 + \log [\text{EDTA}]$ was found to be approximately 0.50. To rationalize the above experimental results and to predict a possible mechanism for the Ce^{IV}-EDTA initiated polymerization inside montmorillonite, following assumptions are made. (i) Intercalated EDTA molecules react fast with Ce^{IV} ions of montmorillonite layered space to form reactive EDTA radicals via an intermediate complex. Due to restricted mobility of Ce^{IV} ions at the negatively charged exchange sites of montmorillonite, the formation constant of the complex is small. The decomposition of the complex is the rate of controlling step. (ii) Polymerization locus is the interlayer space of montmorillonite. The linear termination of growing polymer chain by Ce^{IV} ions is restricted due to their presence in the layered space. (iii) In the acidic and metal ion exchanged aqueous montmorillonite system, a fraction of the intercalated acrylamide molecules present near reacting sites as pairs either through hemisalt formation, where two amide molecules share a proton by means of symmetrical hydrogen bond or/and through weak coordination to the exchanged cations⁶. The protonated as well as the complex amide pairs are at fast equilibrium with unprotonated and free amide molecules respectively, which are defined by a protonation or a formation constant. The initiation step involves the reaction of acrylamide with EDTA radicals, where such monomer pairs are entailed.

Generation of initiator fragment :

(The bar refers to gel phase)

Propagation :

Termination :

Assuming that the intermediate 'complex' is formed very fast and the disproportionation of the complex is rate-controlling following rate expression is derived considering material balance on $[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]$,

$$-d[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = k_d [c] = k_d K [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]_f [\text{R}]$$

where $[c]$ and $[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]_f$ refer to the concentrations of the intermediate complex and the free ceric ions respectively. Therefore,

$$\frac{d[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{k_d K [\text{R}] [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]}{1 + K[\text{R}]} \quad (6)$$

because, $[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}] = [\text{C}] + [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]_f$ and $[\text{C}] = \frac{K[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}][\text{R}]}{1 + K[\text{R}]}$

Using the scheme of reactions and pseudo-steady-state assumption,

$$R_p = \frac{k_p(k_i k_d K K')^{1/2} [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]^{1/2} [\text{R}]^{1/2} [\text{M}]^2}{k_t^{1/2} (k_i K' [\text{M}]^2 + k_i K K' [\text{M}]^2 [\text{R}] + k_t [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}])^{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

($K' (= [\text{M}_2\text{H}^+]/[\text{M}]^2)$) is the apparent protonation constant at a fixed pH (or a formation constant).

The experimental result suggests that the rate of oxidative termination (Step 5) is very slow in the restricted space of the mineral and the last term in the bracket of the denominator may be neglected. Above equation may thus be reduced to

$$R_p = \frac{k_d^{1/2} K^{1/2} k_p / k_t^{1/2} [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]^{1/2} [\text{R}]^{1/2} [\text{M}]}{(1 + K[\text{R}])^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

The concentrations, $[\text{M}]$ and $[\text{R}]$, in montmorillonite gel phase may be given by eqns. (9) and (10),

$$[\text{M}] = L_0^a \theta_M = \frac{L_0^a K_M^a [\text{M}]_s}{1 + K_R^a [\text{R}]_s + K_M^a [\text{M}]_s} \quad (9)$$

$$[\text{M}] = L_0^a \theta_R = \frac{L_0^a K_R^a [\text{M}]_s}{1 + K_R^a [\text{R}]_s + K_M^a [\text{M}]_s} \quad (10)$$

where L_0^a and θ are total active sites in unit volume of montmorillonite gel and the fraction of the total sites occupied by each species, respectively; K_M^a and K_R^a are selectivity coefficients and subscript 's' denotes solution.

Although the concentrations of monomer and EDTA in the solution phase were fixed mostly at 0.4 and 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} , respectively, concentrations of intercalated species must be low due to the presence of water molecules in the interlayer space. Substituting $[\text{M}]$ and $[\text{R}]$ in eqn. (8) in terms to those of eqns. (9) and (10) (assuming the denominators to the approximately unity under present condition), R_p becomes

$$R_p = \frac{k_p K_M^a (L_0^a)^{3/2} (k_d K K_R^a / k_t)^{1/2} [\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]^{1/2} [\text{R}]_s^{1/2} [\text{M}]_s}{(1 + K L_0^a K_R^a [\text{R}]_s)^{1/2}} \quad (11)$$

The concentrations of EDTA used in the present study were low and ranged between 2.5×10^{-3} to 0.01 mol dm^{-3} . In view of the assumption that the complex formation constant (K) in the present condition is also small, the value of $K L_0^a K_R^a [\text{R}]_s$, may be considered insignificant in comparison to unity⁷. Eqn. (11) thus be reduced to

$$R_p = \frac{k_p K_M^a (L_0^a)^{3/2} (k_d K K_R^a / k_t)^{1/2}}{[\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}]^{1/2} [\text{R}]_s^{1/2} [\text{M}]_s} \quad (12)$$

Reviewing the above result, we find that eqn. (12) could satisfactorily account for the present behavior of the $\bar{\text{Ce}}^{\text{IV}}$ -EDTA initialised acrylamide polymerization exhibited in the aqueous montmorillonite layered space.

Experimental

Acrylamide (AM, reagent grade, Fluka) was purified by recrystallization from methanol and dried in vacuum oven at 45° overnight. Cerium(IV) ammonium nitrate, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid salt (EDTA; G.R., E. Merck) were used as received. The method of preparation of H^+ -montmorillonite (HM), Ce^{IV} -montmorillonite (CeM) and the polymerization technique were similar to those reported earlier¹. A separate experiment on the sorption of Ce^{IV} on to montmorillonite showed that the maximum uptake of Ce^{IV} ions by HM sample was nearly 1.0 meq g^{-1} . Molecular weights of the polymer were determined by viscosity measurement in aqueous 0.1 M NaCl solution at 30° using a Ubbelohde viscometer and using the Mark-Houwink relationship⁸,

$$[\eta] = 9.33 \times 10^{-3} M^{0.75} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

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